

**DELIVERABLE 2.6
REPORT ON EFFECTIVE
STRATEGIES TO ENHANCE
ACCESS TO SUSTAINABLE AND
HEALTHY FOOD**

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable analyses the contributions of Food Policy Networks (FPNs) to the creation of healthier, more sustainable and just food systems. FPNs are multi-actor organisations that seek to contribute to more enabling, inclusive and democratic governance contexts. Data collected through 67 interviews with key members of FPNs from around the world offers empirical evidence on the mechanisms deployed to enhance participation of representatives from vulnerable groups in food systems governance and the diversity of transformative strategies utilised.

Our analysis shows that only a few FPNs identify vulnerable groups as primary targets of their interventions. These include food insecure individuals, farmers and residents in rural areas, local food actors (local businesses, community gardens, solidarity kitchens), children, women, migrants and ethnic communities, first peoples (Indigenous communities) and underserved neighbourhoods or areas. Primary inclusion mechanisms are school food programmes, urban and peri-urban agriculture initiatives, organisation of food-related events and food literacy initiatives.

The main barriers to the development and continuity of these initiatives are financial and logistical, which limit the scope and degree of connections that FPNs can create with communities outside their immediate surroundings. In many cases, FPNs develop strategies to identify and circumvent these barriers that are context-based but often share the following objectives: (i) the establishment of collaborative relationships with trusted community organisations, (ii) the implementation and facilitation of inclusive decision-making processes and (iii) the creation of spaces for dialogue.

Findings highlight that FPNs engage with food system transformation primarily through the development of a comprehensive and inclusive perspective on problems and solutions for food and agriculture, prioritising action-oriented agendas and strategies. Through these strategies, FPNs have achieved several policy outcomes, contributing to the development of a food system agenda at the local, regional, national and international levels as well as to the designing of specific ordinances.

Despite these successes, in general FPNs' transformative capacity is hampered by persistent limitations, which make their achievements often isolated and fragile. Barriers such as lack of resources, difficulties of sustaining stakeholder engagement, and navigating changes in elected officials tend to persist. To address these barriers, FPNs have employed a range of place-based strategies that aim at balanced participation of strategic stakeholders (from vulnerable groups to leading policymakers) and the adoption of creative budget solutions (i.e., diversification of funding sources and prioritising essential activities). To further strengthen FPNs contributions to food system transformation, these strategies should be cemented around a wider, transformative agenda that engages critically with the underlying power imbalances that shape the food system.

1. BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

Academic debates on food system transformation have extensively highlighted the importance of creating a more enabling, inclusive and democratic governance context. Within this literature, three interrelated issues have been discussed as potential catalysts of change: multi-actor alliances that cut across science, policy and society (den Boer et al., 2021; Singh et al., 2023); the integration of grassroots food initiatives into policy (Clark et al., 2021; Candel, 2022); and the integration of food policy across departments and councils (Candel and Pereira, 2017; Edwards et al., 2024).

In many ways, “Food Policy Networks” (FPNs) – utilised in this report as an all-encompassing term for multi-actor organisations that aim to transform the food system – embody these promises of change. Indeed, FPNs, and specifically their most formalised and widespread version of “food policy councils”, have been widely portrayed in the literature as governance mechanisms capable of tackling “wicked problems’ that require boundary-spanning relationships” (Bassarab et al., 2019: 32), building a bridge “between the general public’s needs [...] and legislative and regulatory actions” (Packer, 2014: 20; see also Berglund et al., 2021) and making policy processes “more transparent, inclusive and open” (Bassarab et al., 2019: 32).

Drawing on data collected through 67 interviews with representatives from different types of FPNs from around the world, in this report we empirically explore FPNs’ capacity to enhance access to sustainable and healthy food through an innovative focus on the mechanisms deployed to enhance participation of representatives from vulnerable and deprived groups and on the diversity of transformative strategies utilised.

The report is structured around seven main chapters. Following the introduction to the background and aims of the task (Chapter 1), Chapter 2 explains the methodology utilised to collect and analyse data. Chapter 3 presents an overview of the FPNs involved in the research. Chapter 4 analyses findings from the interviews with respect to the FPNs’ strategies for engaging marginalised communities and vulnerable groups. In Chapter 5, results are analysed in relation to the FPNs’ transformative strategies and goals. Chapter 6 discusses barriers encountered by FPNs and provides recommendations to overcome such barriers. The final chapter draws conclusions from the research, with a view to supporting the development of a pan-European FPN platform and feeding into knowledge-sharing workshops with FPNs (WP4).

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. INTERVIEW PREPARATION AND SELECTION

This task builds on three key documents that provide guidance and definitions:

1. The guidelines for the global literature review of FPNs, which was conducted for Task 2.2 of the EU FoodCLIC project (see Appendix);
2. FoodCLIC Deliverable 2.4 (D2.4): *Matrix of Type and Composition of FPNs, their Transformational Capacity and their Engagement with Deprived and Vulnerable Groups* (Edwards et al., 2023); and
3. The interview schedule (see Appendix).

The guidelines for the literature review provided a definition of FPNs and the steps for all partners to identify them (using their respective languages) within designated regions worldwide. D2.4 synthesised the phenomenon of FPNs at the global level, introduced a framework for food system transformation and illustrated diverse examples of FPNs in terms of compositional type, engagement with governmental bodies and type of membership. Together, these two documents provided a unified approach for selecting interviewees and setting the three main themes in the interview schedule (see Appendix).

The Surrey team assigned interviews to each partner from a comprehensive list of over 100 FPN examples outlined in D2.4. Partners selected FPNs based on their diversity, as detailed in Table 1. The interview schedule provided common questions, which covered three main themes: the FPN's purpose and scope; its strategies for inclusion; and its transformative initiatives. Interviewers were encouraged to ask open-ended questions to better understand the FPN's unique context, motivations, challenges and practical experiences. Before conducting interviews, partners were required to undertake their own ethics clearance, which was in line with the requirements of their own institutions.

Initially, 15 FPNs were chosen as case studies, aiming for 4-5 interviews per FPN. However, this approach was later revised to account for different compositional types of FPNs (i.e., boards, alliances or coalitions). As a result of this change, the team identified additional FPNs to achieve the required 50 interviews. Acceptance of interviews varied on the basis of factors such as familiarity with the interviewee or their ability and interest in participating. Some FPNs declined to be interviewed due to resource limitations, concerns about Eurocentrism or perceptions of over-researching. This led to varying coverage across regions, with some countries, such as Spain, Germany and Australia, receiving more attention than others. Although partners were proficient in many languages (i.e., English, Spanish, Italian, German, Portuguese, Dutch and French), regions such as Asia and Eastern Europe remained under-explored due to language constraints.

To address the shortage of interviews, the definition of FPNs was refined through the process to emphasise initiatives aiming to effect policy change for the food system or the urban food environment and comprising diverse stakeholders. From the outcomes of D2.4, the following nuances were identified in FPN types:

- FPNs (such as 'food policy councils' in North America) that do not necessarily focus on city-regions but still target food systems or environmental issues at national or international levels.
- Multi-level FPNs, spanning city-regional and national/international levels.

2.2. DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

In total, 67 semi-structured interviews were conducted (see Table 1 in the next section). These lasted 45 minutes on average, were audio-recorded upon permission and transcribed, often using the free recording feature on MS Teams or Zoom. After proofreading the transcripts, partners translated the interviews into English. Initial coding was undertaken by all partners using the interview schedule, with key points addressing each question/theme collected in a Word document.

To ensure consistency across the data collection, the University of Surrey team requested all partners to upload the transcripts and initial coding documents to a shared MS Teams drive for ongoing verification. Meetings were held intermittently across the data collection period (September 2023 to March 2024), with frequency increasing towards the end of the data collection period. A second analysis focusing on inclusion and transformation issues was conducted by the Surrey team to compile this report.

3. FOOD POLICY NETWORKS: AN OVERVIEW

3.1. FPNS' MAIN CHARACTERISTICS

As shown in Table 1, findings are classified with respect to:

- Regions (number of FPNS): Global (2), Northern America and Canada (5), Central and South America (7), Australia and New Zealand (6), UK and Ireland (9), Asia (4), Africa (6), Europe (2), Central Europe (7), Mediterranean Europe (12) and Northern Europe (7).
- Types of FPNS (number of FPNS): **Networks** (17), **Councils** (17), **Committees** (8), **Partnerships** (6), **Platforms** (5), **Alliances** (4), **Coalitions** (3), **Tables** (3), **Groups** (2) and **Labs** (2).

Table 1: FPNS included in this study by region (first column) and classified by case study (last column).

Region	N°	Scale	Name of FPN	Case study
Global	1	Global	Food Systems, C40 Cities Climate Leadership Group	Group
	2		Nutrition in City Ecosystems (NICE) (Bangladesh, Kenya and Rwanda)	Platform
America - northern & Canada	3	National	Food Secure Canada	Network
	4	Regional	San Diego Food System Alliance (USA)	Alliance
	5	City-regional	Healthy Savannah (USA)	Partnership
	6		Denver Sustainable Food Policy Council (USA)	Council
	7		Chicago Food Policy Action Council (USA)	Council
America - central & south	8	National	La Plataforma Estratégica contra el Sobrepeso y la Obesidad (Mexico)	Platform
	9		Grupo Interinstitucional de Paisajes Alimentarios Sostenibles (GIPASOS, Nicaragua)	Group
	10	Regional	Network of Agroecological and Peripheral Female Urban Farmers (Brazil)	Network
	11		Teia dos Povos Network, southern Bahia (Brazil)	Network
	12		City-regional	Comité Municipal de Seguridad Alimentaria, La Paz and El Alto (Bolivia)

	13		Programa de Sistemas Alimentarios Sostenibles, Plataforma multi-actor, Lima and Huancayo (Peru)	Platform
	14		Pacto Agro-alimentario de Quito (Ecuador)	Platform
Australia & New Zealand	15	National	Sustain: The Australian Food Network	Network
	16		Australian Food Sovereignty Alliance (AFSA)	Alliance
	17		Open Food Network (Australia and New Zealand)	Network
	18	Regional	Food Fairness Illawarra (Australia)	Coalition
	19	City-regional	Our Food Network, Ōtepoti / Dunedin (New Zealand)	Network
	20		Edible Canterbury (New Zealand)	Partnership
UK & Ireland	21	National	Sustainable Food Places (UK)	Network
	22		Scottish Food Coalition	Coalition
	23		Nourish Scotland	Network
	24	City-regional	Greater Manchester Food Security Action Network (England)	Network
	25		Good Food Greater Manchester (England)	Partnership
	26		Sheffield's Food Partnership, ShefFood (England)	Partnership
	27		Cork Food Policy Council (Ireland)	Council
	28		Bwyd Abertawe (Wales)	Partnership
	29	Urban	Islington Food Partnership, London (England)	Partnership
Asia	30	National	Good Food Fund China	Network
	31		Health Promotion Foundation Nonthaburi and Chiang Mai (Thailand)	Council
	32	City-regional	City Strategic Agenda, Amman (Jordan)	Committee
	33		Food Smart City, Surakarta (Indonesia)	Platform
Africa	34	City-regional	Food Liaison Advisory Council (FLAC), Kisumu (Kenya)	Council
	35		Mbale Good Food Council and Parliament (Uganda)	Council
	36		Lusaka Food Policy Council (Zambia)	Council
	37		Comité d'initiatives pour la gouvernance alimentaire (CIGA) de la Commune de Bambilor (Senegal)	Committee
	38		Uganda Food Change Lab, Fort Portal (Uganda)	Lab
	39		Arusha Food Safety Committee (Tanzania)	Committee
Europe	40	Continental	Good Food Good Farming (GFGF)	Alliance
	41		EU Food Policy Coalition	Coalition

Europe - central	42	National	Ernährungszukunft Schweiz (Switzerland)	Council
	43		Biostädte Netzwerk (Germany)	Network
	44	City-regional	Ernährungsforum Bern (Switzerland)	Network
	45		Ernährungsforum Zurich (Switzerland)	Network
	46		Ernährungsrat Wien (Austria)	Council
	47		Ernährungsrat Oldenburg (Germany)	Council
	48		Ernährungsrat Freiburg (Germany)	Council
Europe - mediterranean	49	National	Red de Municipios por la Agroecología (Spain)	Network
	50		Rete PunTO al Cibo (Italy)	Network
	51		Alimentar Cidades Sustentáveis (Portugal)	Network
	52	City-regional	Mesa de Coordinación del Pacto de Milán, Córdoba (Spain)	Table
	53		Consell Alimentari Municipal de València (Spain)	Council
	54		Consejo Alimentario Municipal de Zaragoza (Spain)	Council
	55		Nutrire Trento - Food Policy di Trento (Italy)	Table
	56		Comitato promotore per una food policy di Roma (Italy)	Committee
	57		Bergamo Food Policy (Italy)	Table
	58		Politique Agricole et Alimentaire Comunale (PAC, comité) de Plessé (France)	Committee
	59		Projet Alimentaire Territorial (PAT) de la Métropole Aix-Marseille-Provence et du Pays d'Arles (France)	Committee
	60		Projet Alimentaire Territorial (PAT) de Nantes Métropole (France)	Committee
	Europe - northern	61	City-regional	Bruges Food Lab (Belgium)
62		Ceinture Aliment-Terre Liègeoise (Belgium)		Network
63			Ghent Food Policy Council (Belgium)	Council
64			Voedsel Anders (The Netherlands)	Network
65			Ede Food Council (The Netherlands)	Council
66			Haarlem Food Future (The Netherlands)	Alliance
67			Ons Eten Den Haag (The Netherlands)	Council

The case studies were identified primarily on the basis of the inclusion of the specific term in their name or of their self-definition from their website or interviews. The top four classifications were:

- *Networks* are characterised by openness and a loose structure in terms of purpose and membership. They encompass a wide range of themes – including agroecology, food security, food democracy and sustainable cities. Some networks also include a "council" within their structure.
- *Councils* were initially popularised in the USA and later spread to many other countries. Councils reflect diverse configurations in terms of membership composition, policy and programme activities and geographical scope.
- *Committees* are commonly integrated into municipalities.
- *Partnerships* are often associated with FPNs in the UK.

The diversity of FPN types and case studies reflects variations in scale, initiation (grassroots, government or company-led), longevity (i.e., Food Secure Canada is one of the oldest), membership and formalisation levels. These variations, which are discussed in D2.4, highlight shifts in key themes and purposes (from food security to broader food systems perspectives) and differences in regional approaches.

3.2. FPNS' RELATIONSHIP WITH GOVERNMENT

Understanding the impact of FPNs on food system transformation through policy requires insight into their relationship with government. Among the 67 FPNs interviewed, nine are based 'inside' the local or regional government, meaning they are physically located within government entities, initiated or led by government bodies. Examples include:

- *Biostädte Netzwerk* (Germany), housed within city government in partner cities, receiving funding from the city and with additional support from federal or state governments.
- *Consell Alimentari Municipal de València* (Spain), where the council operates within the municipality to ensure the involvement of the administration.
- *PAC Comité de Plessé* (France), representing official municipal policy with leadership from the municipality in dialogue with civil society.
- The *Greater Manchester Food Security Action Network* (England), integrated into the Combined Authorities in the country.

Only three FPNs were resolutely 'outside' of government, not being associated with or reliant upon government in any way. An example is Nicaragua, where, as stated by the interviewee, "*a political mandate [dictates that] there cannot be a relationship between state institutions and this type of initiative*". The *Teia dos Povos Network's* (Brazil) interviewee emphasised their separation from government as integral to their identity and purpose.

Most FPNs, however, exist "in between," neither fully inside nor outside government, with different strategies to engage with and influence policy (see Table 2). These include:

- Focus on policy for food system transformation or other approaches.
- Formal to informal involvement of government actors.
- Co-production of policy documents with government.
- Transitioning from municipal affiliation to independent FPN status.

Table 2. FPNs and government involvement.

N°	(Short) Name	'Within'	'In between' (from most to least engagement with government) *						'Outside'
			Initiated By	Formal recognition by	Include government members	Co-write / consult / monitoring	Funded / supported by government	Broker to share views	
1	C40 Cities				x				
2	NICE				x				
3	Food Secure							x	
4	San Diego FSA		x						
5	Healthy Savannah		x					x	
6	Denver SFPC	x							
7	Chicago FPAC						x		
8	ContraPESO								x
9	GIPASOS								x
10	Network Brazil						x		
11	Teia dos Povos								x
12	Comité La Paz (El Alto)				x				x
13	Platforms Peru					x			
14	Pacto Quito				x				
15	Sustain Australia					x	x		

36	Lukasa FPC	x							
37	CIGA				x				
38	Uganda Lab				x				
39	Arusha FSC	x							
40	GFGF								x
41	EU FPC								x
42	EZ Switzerland				x				
43	Biostädte	x							
44	EF Bern								x
45	EF Zurich							x	
46	ER Wien		x			x			
47	ER Oldenburg							x	
48	ER Freiburg		x			x			
49	Red Municipios		x	x		x			
50	Rete PunTO					x			
51	Alimentar Cidades							x	
52	Mesa Córdoba				x				
53	Consell València	x							
54	Consejo Zaragoza	x							
55	Nutrire Trento	x							

56	Comitato Roma					x				
57	Bergamo FP				x					
58	PAC Plessé	x								
59	PAT Marseille	x		x				x		
60	PAT Nantes	x								
61	Bruges Lab				x	x				
62	CAT Liègeoise					x				
63	Ghent FPC					x		x		
64	Voedsel Anders							x		
65	Ede Food Council					x				
66	Harleem Future					x				
67	Ons Eten					x		x		
	TOTAL	11	3	5	15	19	15	7	5	5

*'Within': FPNs are institutionally located within a government department or agency; 'Initiated by': FPNs were created as a result of government legislation; 'Formal recognition by': Official legal recognition status by the government; 'Includes government members': Government employees or elected officials are members of FPNs or participate in some capacity; 'Co-write, consult, monitoring': FPNs act in an advisory role on matters of food policy; 'Funded/supported by government': FPNs receive in-kind support from government bodies such as administrative help or receive funding from public grants; 'Broker to share views': FPNs act in a facilitator role to bring together viewpoints from across the food system, including government actors; 'Provide independent submissions': FPNs submit policy briefs that provides specific food policy recommendations or evaluate current policies addressing food issues; and 'Outside': FPNs have no relation to government.

4. APPROACHES FOR ENGAGING MARGINALISED COMMUNITIES AND VULNERABLE GROUPS

It is widely argued in the literature that certain groups encounter systemic and institutional barriers, are frequently neglected by authorities and other stakeholders and feel disempowered within the food system (see, for example, Gaupp et al., 2021). FPNs, through their collaborative efforts across sectors and places, can play a crucial role in empowering these groups, enhancing food accessibility and fostering equality. In this chapter, we delve into the specific groups assisted by FPNs and their approaches to include them by raising the following questions:

- What groups and communities are targeted and supported by FPNs?
- How do FPNs involve diverse marginalised communities or vulnerable groups in internal processes and procedures?
- What specific policy interventions do FPNs employ to engage with marginalised communities or vulnerable groups?
- What obstacles do FPNs encounter in their efforts to achieve greater inclusivity, and how can they enhance their inclusiveness?

4.1. DEFINING MARGINALISED COMMUNITIES AND VULNERABLE GROUPS

Our findings show that, although FPNs generally define themselves as inclusive and open and frequently utilise terms such as “disadvantaged populations” or “vulnerable groups” in their narratives, most lack a specific focus or clear definition of marginalised communities. Indeed, only a few FPNs target specific groups and communities, reflecting the varied challenges and needs across different regions. These include:

- **Food insecure individuals:** There is a clear emphasis on supporting disadvantaged families, homeless individuals, and people in long-term unemployment as part of a broader commitment to addressing social inequalities. Some examples of FPNs that focus on food insecure individuals include the Cork Food Policy Council (Ireland), the Chicago Food Policy Action Council (USA), and the *Ghent Food Policy Council* (Belgium).

- **Farmers and rural areas:** Some FPNs focus on supporting farmers and rural communities through initiatives targeting young farmers (such as the *EU Food Policy Coalition*), peri-urban farming families (as in the case of *Comité Municipal de Seguridad Alimentaria in La Paz*, Bolivia) or women engaged in urban and peri-urban farming (*Network of Agroecological and Peripheral Female Urban Farmers*, Brazil). In Bern (Switzerland), the *Ernährungsforum* also target right-wing farmer groups to include them in their dialogues.
- **Local food actors:** Engagement with local food actors is common, reflecting a pervasive emphasis on promoting sustainable food production and supporting small businesses. In Surakarta (Indonesia), for instance, *Food Smart City* focuses on connecting local businesses to strengthen the local food system, whereas the *Food Liaison Advisory Council's (FLAC, Kisumu, Kenya)* membership purposefully includes stakeholders from across the value chain.
- **Children:** Efforts to support children's food security and nutrition are evident across various regions, indicating a commitment to addressing inter-generational poverty and health disparities. Schools, in particular, are the target of FPNs' interventions in China (*Good Food Fund*), Dunedin (*Our Food Network Dunedin*, New Zealand), Canterbury (*Edible Canterbury*, New Zealand) and Mexico (*ContraPESO*).
- **Women:** FPNs across various regions target gender inequalities within their internal governance structure and in outward-facing programmes and policy activities. For example, the *San Diego Food System Alliance (USA)* made deliberate efforts to centre the voices of women, particularly women of colour, in their governance and leadership structure. Similarly, in Zambia, the *Lusaka Food Policy Council* established a Gender Social Inclusion Policy to ensure the needs of different groups of people (i.e., women) are considered in planning and decision-making processes.
- **Migrants and ethnic communities:** FPNs in North America, the UK and New Zealand recognise the specific challenges faced by migrant and ethnic communities, with efforts directed towards inclusion and cultural sensitivity in food policies and programs. For instance, *Healthy Savannah (USA)* prioritises supporting Black and Hispanic populations, reflecting local demographics.
- **First peoples (Indigenous communities):** Indigenous communities are particularly relevant for FPNs in North America, South America, New Zealand and Australia. For example, *Teia dos Povos Network (Brazil)* centralises defending land natural resources rights for indigenous communities in the work of the FPN.
- **Specific neighbourhoods or areas:** Some FPNs target interventions towards specific spatial areas, tailoring support to address localised food insecurity and socio-economic challenges. Examples of this approach include *Consejo Alimentario Municipal de Zaragoza (Spain)* and *Comité Municipal de Seguridad Alimentaria (La Paz, Bolivia)*.
- **Others:** Other groups mentioned by single FPNs include religious groups (*Food Change Lab, Uganda*), the LGBTQ+ community (*Teia dos Povos Network, Brazil*), people with disabilities (in *Our Food Network Dunedin, New Zealand*), and the middle-class due to their vulnerability

to unhealthy food environments (Good Food Fund, China). Three interviewees also identified youth as a vulnerable group.

Contrary to assumptions made in the literature, FPNs are not invariably inclusive; our research identified examples of FPNs that deliberately exclude certain actors from their membership. This is the case, for instance, of the *EU Food Policy Coalition*, which excludes businesses, preferring to focus solely on civil society organisations to ensure their message aligns with their vision.

In summary, FPNs demonstrate a broad commitment to supporting marginalised communities and vulnerable groups, encompassing a wide range of demographics and socio-economic backgrounds. In general, FPNs primarily engage with organisations that work directly with marginalised communities, rather than with the communities themselves. For instance, in El Alto (Bolivia), the *Comité Municipal de Seguridad Alimentaria* collaborate with institutions supporting vulnerable families, rather than engaging directly with them; similarly, the *Islington Food Partnership* (England) reaches out to people who are connected to communities at risk of exclusion.

“So, engagement through targeting the right spatial areas and hence the right target demographic, then listening to what they say through the annual survey, then employing people from the community to work for Healthy Savannah.” (Interviewee, Healthy Savannah, USA)

4.2. INCLUSIVE PARTICIPATION WITHIN FPNs

Inclusive participation within FPNs entails actively involving marginalised communities and vulnerable groups in internal processes and procedures. This chapter analyses FPNs operating at different scales (i.e., global and continental, national and regional, city-regional and urban) in relation to the degree of participation of different marginalised communities or vulnerable groups (Table 3).

Table 3: Degree of participation within the FPNs framework (based on Luyet et al., 2012).

Degree of participation	Description
Information	Knowledge-sharing about the FPN and its initiatives
Consultation	Presentation of the FPN’s approach or goals and collection of suggestions, which can be taken into account or ignored for internal decision-making
Collaboration	Presentation of the FPN’s approach and goals and collection of suggestions, which are taken into account for internal decision-making
Co-decision	Involvement throughout the processes of developing approaches, goals and initiatives as well as decision-making
Empowerment	Delegation of decision-making over the FPN’s approach, goals and initiatives

Global and continental FPNs

The four global and continental FPNs reported different strategies to involve marginalised communities or vulnerable groups in their internal processes. In the case of *Nutrition in City Ecosystems (NICE)*, there is a deliberate effort to ensure gender and age diversity within the FPN and empower members through representation. This involves conducting vulnerability assessments and mapping vulnerable female and youth groups in urban areas. Capacity-building sessions are organised to empower these groups, enabling them to actively engage in the initiatives and activities of the FPN.

In Europe, the *EU Food Policy Coalition* only includes civil society organisations as part of its mission to empower non-governmental actors in shaping food policies and initiatives. The *Good Food Good Farming (GFGF)* also includes various stakeholders through consultation processes, particularly those representing rural and agricultural interests. The *GFGF* prioritises the inclusion of rural groups (such as small-scale and agroecological farmers) in its internal discussions to ensure that their concerns and perspectives are considered in food policy discourses.

“We try to strengthen their [farmers] voices in the discourse [...] and include their perspectives and make sure that our messaging also appeals to them.” (Interviewee, GFGF, Europe)

National and regional FPNs

Whereas national networks of cities such as *Red de Municipios por la Agroecología* in Spain and the *Biostädte Netzwerk* in Germany focus on inclusion within specific urban areas and projects rather than as an overarching goal, others employ specific strategies to ensure inclusive participation within their FPNs.

Some FPNs prioritise disseminating and sharing information about their internal structures and activities. For instance, the *Alimentar Cidades Sustentáveis* in Portugal focuses on openly sharing information with the community. Although it lacks a specific focus on vulnerable groups, this FPN organises webinars to raise awareness and train individuals from disadvantaged communities. The *Australian Food Sovereignty Alliance (AFSA)* also provides information about pro bono memberships and democratic engagement opportunities for First Peoples.

Other FPNs engage in consultation processes, presenting their approaches and goals and soliciting input and suggestions from stakeholders. *Food Secure Canada*, for example, allocates space and financial support to Black and Indigenous groups, recognising their priorities and incorporating their input into decision-making processes. *Nourish Scotland* also emphasises meaningful participation, offering consultation services, workshops and funding for “dignity projects” that are aimed at understanding and addressing community needs.

Certain FPNs emphasise collaboration with external partners and stakeholders to address food-related challenges. For example, *Food Fairness Illawarra* (Australia) collaborates with food-relief agencies to connect with communities in need. Similarly, *Nourish Scotland* engages with industry organisations while maintaining close ties with civil society to ensure the representation of constituent groups in its activities.

Ernährungszukunft in Switzerland stands out for actively pursuing the inclusion of various groups in co-decision processes. This FPN prioritises representative and inclusive recruitment. By outsourcing recruitment to a survey organisation, they ensure a broad spectrum of participants from different regions, genders, educational backgrounds and even political views.

“Engagement is more of a ‘try to go to them and ask what do you want us to do?’ That’s probably more of our strategy [...] we converge every year in a democratic space at a cost that anyone can afford, and we actually make it free if you can’t afford it. We also have solidarity sessions online every month, and you all could just come to any of those things.”
(Interviewee, AFSA, Australia)

Other FPNs, such as the *Network of Agroecological and Peripheral Female Urban Farmers* (Brazil) and *AFSA* (Australia), specifically focus on women’s leadership, offering pro bono memberships and democratic spaces for engagement, including solidarity sessions or affordable events.

Finally, the *Scottish Food Coalition* strives to represent a diverse range of farmers and engages with industry organisations and civil society to ensure that constituent groups are adequately represented in its activities.

City-regional and urban FPNs

Some FPNs at the city-regional and urban scales prioritise sharing information about their initiatives and activities with their local communities. For example, the *Uganda Food Change Lab* involves diverse stakeholders in quarterly meetings to share ideas, challenges and solutions, ensuring inclusivity through associations and committees representing various groups. FPNs such as *Ernährungsforum Bern* (Switzerland) and the *Denver Sustainable Food Policy Council* (USA) create open and neutral spaces for dialogue, inviting diverse stakeholders to engage in discussions. For instance, the “Food Talks” event series in Bern welcomes speakers from various backgrounds, including members of different political parties, to foster dialogue. Similarly, the *Denver Sustainable Food Policy Council* (USA) ensures inclusivity by translating meetings into Spanish, promoting engagement through social media and establishing a race and equity working group to examine decision-making processes.

Other FPNs engage in consultation processes, seeking input and suggestions from stakeholders to inform decision-making. For instance, the *City Strategic Agenda* in Amman (Jordan) organises workshops and interviews with civil society members and the private sector to understand their interests and needs in relation to projects such as central markets and public parks. Similarly, the *Consejo Alimentario Municipal de Zaragoza* (Spain) collaborates with city council technicians to promote the right to food among vulnerable populations. Another example is the Gender Social Inclusion Policy as part of the *Lusaka Food Policy Council* (Zambia), which aims to identify barriers affecting diverse social groups in food security planning and decision-making processes.

Certain FPNs emphasise collaboration with external partners and stakeholders to address food-related challenges. For instance, the *Comité Municipal de Seguridad Alimentaria* in La Paz (Bolivia) cooperates with rural and peri-urban communities of producers, including them in discussions and supporting their needs. Similarly, the *Islington Food Partnership* (England) collaborates with representatives of community organisations, such as food banks and cultural associations, to incorporate the lived experiences of deprived citizens into decision-making processes.

FPNs such as those in San Diego and Savannah (USA) empower communities by prioritising their voices and needs in decision-making processes. The *San Diego Food System Alliance* (USA), in particular, focuses on building relationships with targeted communities and balancing the leadership ratio to better represent farmers, food business owners and historically disadvantaged communities. Similarly, *Healthy Savannah* (USA) targets specific neighbourhoods, conducts annual surveys and employs people from disadvantaged communities.

Generally, some interviewees see their FPNs as a bridge between local governments and marginalised actors and communities. For

example, *FLAC's* (Kenya) membership includes stakeholders from the entire food value chain, and this collective involvement has been pivotal in shaping county-level food systems policies.

“Our focus is really on building relationships with priority communities and then bringing them kind of into the fold [...] ensuring that kind of shifting the ratio within this community and bringing in more farmers, more food business owners, more folks [...] elevating the voices of people most impacted by inequities in the food system [...] like farm workers and farmers, food business owners, fishermen, ranchers and communities of colour [...] We're primarily a women of colour-led organization as well as our Board of Directors. So, it's very foundational to our work and in terms of who we're serving.”
(Interviewee, San Diego Food System Alliance, USA)

4.3. POLICY INTERVENTIONS TARGETING SPECIFIC GROUPS

Interviewees recognised that engaging with marginalised communities or vulnerable groups through activities and projects is often easier than through membership. Most FPNs work with other organisations that are either part of the FPN or collaborate with it. These organisations typically organise activities targeting marginalised groups. For instance, *Bwyd Abertawe* (Wales) actively collaborates with community organisations delivering services to low-income and ethnically diverse communities, ensuring inclusivity in their projects. As explained in the interview, this collaborative effort facilitates the identification of specific needs within these communities and helps to tailor interventions accordingly.

In general, interviewees identified a diverse range of policy interventions that FPNs employ to engage with marginalised communities or vulnerable groups, which are framed around specific themes that reflect the needs of the local communities as well as the FPNs' priorities. Based on the interviews, the following themes are particularly prominent:

Theme 1: Access to food, right to food

FPNs recognise that, although access to food is a fundamental human right, many communities and groups still face barriers to securing nutritious food. To address this issue, FPNs adopt a wide range of strategies to improve food access and security. For instance, the *Network of Agroecological and Peripheral Female Urban Farmers* (Brazil) collaborate with local organisations to

distribute nutritious food baskets to vulnerable families; *Nutrire Trento* (Italy) utilises a solidarity fund to provide vouchers to families, enabling them to purchase goods from local markets. *Food Fairness Illawarra* (Australia) works with food relief agencies and NGOs to provide free lunches – an intervention that, as explained by the interviewee, also brings people together, thereby strengthening social inclusion and community building. The *Bruges Food Lab* (Belgium) offers meals at lower prices and includes more plant-based protein in meals provided by welfare services. Finally, *Nourish Scotland* focuses on addressing barriers to accessing healthy food, distributing free veggie boxes to low-income individuals and providing feedback to local schemes for broader accessibility. In addition to enhancing access to food, these initiatives also empower individuals and communities to make healthier food choices.

“There is also, for example, the federation of neighbourhood associations, which at first did not have much connection with the agri-food issue, however, they have entered quite strongly with the issue of the right to food. Above all, in inclusive neighbourhoods, and there have been community cooking workshops, we have done a lot of little things between the different entities that are at the table.” (Interviewee, Mesa de Coordinación del Pacto de Milán, Córdoba, Spain)

Theme 2: School food programmes

Recognising that schools play a crucial role in shaping children's dietary habits and food preferences and raising awareness, FPNs implement initiatives to improve the quality of food provided in schools, particularly in lower decile schools where students may face greater food insecurity. For example, *Edible Canterbury* and *Our Food Network Dunedin* (New Zealand) focus on establishing food forests and school gardens, providing students in lower decile schools with access to fresh, locally grown produce and valuable educational opportunities. The *PAC Comité de Plessé* (France) promotes locally produced and healthy food in school canteens and collaborates with small-scale local producers. The FPN in Mexico advocates for more nutritious options in school shops and concessions, aiming to improve the nutritional quality of food available to students.

“Our stakeholders that we work with, they also work with like, you know, people in underprivileged areas and sectors, for example, chefs, schools, and, you know, schools of left behind children. And so those definitely are on, you know, on our agenda. And also, you know, not only because we think they're important to talk about it, but it's also something that the government has policies to help them” (Interviewee, Good Food Fund China)

Theme 3: Urban and peri-urban agriculture

Urban and peri-urban agriculture initiatives play a vital role in increasing food security and promoting community resilience, particularly in urban areas where access to fresh produce may be limited. For example, the *Health Promotion Foundation* (Thailand) collaborates with municipal authorities to allocate land for urban gardening projects, providing residents with space to grow food and connect with nature. Similarly, *Our Food Network Dunedin's* (New Zealand) family garden project focuses on social housing communities, providing residents with resources and support to start their own gardens, empowering marginalised communities to grow their own food and

fostering community ownership and self-sufficiency. AFSA (Kenya) focuses on addressing challenges related to land tenure and promoting youth engagement in farming to increase food production, whereas the *City Strategic Agenda's* (Jordan) urban agriculture projects target low-income neighbourhoods and refugees. Regarding peri-urban agriculture, the *Comité Municipal de Seguridad Alimentaria in La Paz* (Bolivia) works to connect families from the rural hinterland to city markets.

Theme 4: Community food-related events

FPNs organise events to foster community engagement and solidarity. For example, *Edible Canterbury's* (New Zealand) community feast brings together over 300 people, including homeless individuals, to share a meal and build connections. Similarly, the *Chicago Food Policy Action Council* (USA) organises an annual summit to facilitate collaboration and knowledge-sharing between stakeholders in the food system. The *San Diego Food System Alliance* (USA) prioritises community outreach, offering stipends and scholarships for events to ensure inclusivity and accessibility, thereby creating opportunities for individuals and communities to come together, raise awareness of food insecurity issues and promote collective action.

"We do it [event] mid-February, usually when it's kind of a soft time in the food system work, particularly for producers. Because midwinter. You know the folks have had a chance to recover after the season, and it's just before planting season really kicks in. So, it's a good kind of gap also in other conferences and events for folks to come together." (Interviewee, Chicago Food Policy Action Council, USA)

Theme 5: Educating about healthy and sustainable food

Educational initiatives play a crucial role in promoting healthy and sustainable food practices, empowering individuals and communities to make informed choices about their diet and lifestyle. For example, the *Cork Food Policy Council* (Ireland) invests in nutrition workers to educate communities on healthy eating and food poverty, providing resources and support to promote positive behaviour change. Similarly, the *Comité d'initiatives pour la gouvernance alimentaire* (CIGA) de la Commune de Bambilor (Senegal) focuses on training children, women and farmers in food and nutrition, promoting self-sufficiency and agroecological practices. The *Consejo Alimentario Municipal de Zaragoza* (Spain) conducts training sessions in collaboration with community health networks, focusing on sustainable and healthy eating habits, and involves various groups, such as elderly people and vulnerable families, in the training process.

"We have a new Healthy Communities Coordinator, and she's been given a budget to employ a community nutrition worker [...] they will very actively take on a food poverty role and work directly with communities [...] and hopefully work with [Name] in terms of community growing." (Interviewee, Cork Food Policy Council, Ireland)

4.4. CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING INCLUSION

Navigating challenges to inclusion

In the pursuit of greater inclusivity, FPNs encounter a myriad of obstacles that hinder their efforts to involve diverse communities and ensure equitable participation.

- 1) **Breaking out of insular bubbles:** The challenge of reaching beyond existing networks and engaging with diverse communities is multifaceted. *Ernährungsforum Bern* (Switzerland) highlighted this issue, emphasising the need to transcend existing networks and connect with people outside traditional spheres. The concept of "getting out of the bubble" underscores the difficulty of reaching marginalised communities and forging meaningful connections with them. This sentiment is echoed by the *Mesa de Coordinación del Pacto de Milán de Córdoba* (Spain), who noted that professionalised meeting spaces may discourage individuals who feel disconnected from the decision-making processes or perceive limited opportunities for meaningful engagement. Interviewees from *Our Food Network Dunedin* (New Zealand) and the *Islington Food Partnership* (England) also recognised the difficulties of reaching certain groups due to lack of local engagement or language barriers.
- 2) **Resource constraints:** Limited funding and resources pose significant barriers to fostering inclusivity within FPNs. Some interviewees emphasised the critical role of financial support in enabling outreach efforts and accommodating diverse voices. Without adequate resources, FPNs struggle to organise events, provide translation services or support the participation of marginalised communities, thus perpetuating existing inequities. *Ernährungsrat Oldenburg* (Germany), for instance, struggles in offering free activities to promote accessibility, while the interviewee from *FLAC* (Kenya) acknowledged the need for funding to facilitate regular convening, particularly for members of marginalised rural communities, who require support for transportation. The *Denver Sustainable Food Policy Council's* (USA) dilemma regarding interpretation services highlighted the logistical challenges of accommodating diversity, which further exacerbates barriers to participation.
- 3) **Representation and accessibility:** Balancing the need for diverse representation with the logistical challenges of inclusive participation presents a complex dilemma for FPNs. *Food Secure Canada's* interviewee recognised the diversity within communities, underscoring the importance of avoiding tokenism and ensuring genuine representation. However, achieving this balance proves challenging, as illustrated by *Food Fairness Illawarra's* (Australia) struggle to create a supportive environment for individuals amidst the dominance of organisational representatives. The interviewee from the *San Diego Food System Alliance* (USA) also recognised power dynamics within the FPN and highlighted the importance of

being mindful and respectful, ensuring everyone has a legitimate voice in decision-making processes.

“We need a black food movement. We need an indigenous food movement. We need, you know, people of Chinese origin food movement. You know, people all have their own stories and their own histories. [...] generalising is also like really problematic. [...] What we’re struggling with is how you move from that to the food movement being all of those voices. And what kind of fora and what kind of mechanisms and processes and what kind of outcomes.” (Interviewee, Food Secure Canada)

Strategies for enhanced inclusivity

Through community partnerships, inclusive decision-making processes and dialogue-driven approaches, FPNs aim to create more equitable and responsive food systems that reflect the diverse needs and perspectives of all stakeholders, as explained below.

- 1) Community partnerships:** Collaborating with trusted community organisations and leaders emerges as a promising strategy for overcoming barriers to inclusivity. By leveraging existing relationships and local knowledge, FPNs can tailor their outreach efforts to meet the specific needs and priorities of diverse communities. This approach fosters trust, enhances accessibility and facilitates meaningful engagement, as evidenced, for example, by the *San Diego Food System Alliance's* (USA) success in partnering with community-based organisations. *ShefFood* (England) also collaborates with community leaders to develop approaches that resonate with vulnerable communities, ensuring that engagement efforts are led by community needs, rather than by preconceived notions. Spatial inclusion is also considered important in overcoming existing barriers, as emphasised by the example of the *Network of Agroecological and Peripheral Female Urban Farmers* (Brazil), which fosters territorial food sovereignty to create spaces where everybody can feel welcome.
- 2) Inclusive decision-making:** Inclusive decision-making processes and equitable resource allocation are essential for promoting diversity within FPNs. *Lusaka Food Policy Council's* (Zambia) emphasis on gender-sensitive approaches and *Food Secure Canada's* recognition of intersectionality highlights the importance of considering the diverse needs and experiences of stakeholders. By creating opportunities for diverse voices to be heard and valued, FPNs can cultivate a more inclusive and representative decision-making culture.
- 3) Feedback mechanisms and dialogue:** Establishing feedback mechanisms and creating spaces for dialogue and collaboration are critical to fostering inclusivity. *ShefFood's* (England) initiative to involve diverse communities in policy development exemplifies a commitment to co-creation and community-driven solutions. By actively soliciting input from under-represented groups and prioritising their perspectives, FPNs can ensure that

“An iterative process is meaningful participatory engagements that should define both the food partnership and its subsequent strategy. So, that ranges in different types from sort of big stakeholder events like food summits, but it could be things like community food surveys and community food mapping.” (Interviewee, Sustainable Food Places, UK)

their initiatives reflect the needs and aspirations of all stakeholders. *Bwyd Abertawe* (Wales), for instance, emphasises dialogue to develop trust and relationships with farmers, recognising their critical role in shaping sustainable food systems.

5. APPROACHES TO FOOD SYSTEM TRANSFORMATION

This section explores FPNs' approaches to transforming the food system by raising the following questions:

- What are the overarching transformational goals of FPNs?
- How do FPNs engage with governmental bodies in pursuit of their goals?
- What specific policy interventions do FPNs employ and how do they influence and contribute to food system transformation?

5.1. FPNs' TRANSFORMATIONAL GOALS

Even though “transformation” is not often expressed in clear or specific terms by the FPNs¹ (D2.4; Edwards, et al., 2024), the interview data reveals that FPNs position themselves as “catalysts/ brokers/collaborators” (*Good Food Fund China*), “advocates” (*Food Fairness Illawarra*, Australia), “re-valuers/ empowerers” of people, produce and places (*Teia dos Povos Network*, Brazil) or as “innovators” towards creating healthy, just and more sustainable food systems (*Good Food Fund China*).² These labels, combined with insights from the interviews, help to identify the following key trends in FPNs' goals:

- Shifting from a focus on food security to a broader food system perspective;
- Representing and empowering vulnerable and marginalised groups; and
- Transitioning from discourse to action.

In all, our analysis suggests that FPNs worldwide are striving to become more comprehensive, inclusive and action oriented. The following section explores how these goals can be achieved by examining FPNs' relationship with the government for policy change.

¹ There are some exceptions, such as the *San Diego Food System Alliance* who has a ‘theory of change’ document. However, such a singular document is difficult to correlate against the greater number of FPNs for data analysis.

² To note that some FPNs sit within organisational programs, such as RIKOLTO (Nicaragua, Peru, Ecuador, Indonesia), the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact or the C40 Cities Program, which all specify top-level goals as a condition of membership.

5.2. POLICY IMPACT AT DIFFERENT SCALES

Building on the framework of transformational capacity of FPNs presented in D2.4 (den Boer et al. 2023), this section analyses policy interventions in relation to the scale of FPNs (i.e., global, continental, national, regional, city-regional and urban), recognising the relevance of various levels of change (Table 4).

Table 2: *The transformational capacity of FPNs (den Boer et al. 2023)*

Levels of change	Description
Non-systemic intermediation in-between individual entities	Actions occurring between individual actors, organisations or projects to gain information or knowledge or access to resources.
Systemic intermediation facilitating 'horizontal interactions'	Actions occurring within a single FPN and between entities from different FPNs sharing similar goals, such as the exchange of knowledge, which can catalyse activities within and between FPNs.
Systemic intermediation facilitating 'vertical interactions'	Actions occurring between FPNs and between their related institutions to initiate or support processes of institutional change. This can entail disrupting norms, values, laws, regulations and standards, thereby stimulating new visions and expectations, initiating policy renewal and acting as an impartial voice for new FPNs.

Global and continental FPNs

FPNs operating at broad and multi-level scales can be highly effective in facilitating change from conception to implementation, as shown by the example of the *C40 Food Systems Network*. However, many FPNs encounter challenges in representing diverse interests across broad regions. Consequently, they often seek varied approaches to unite this diversity around a common goal. For example, at the European-level, FPNs such as *GFGF* and the *EU Food Policy Coalition* complement each other by adopting an awareness-raising and evidence-based approach. *GFGF* leads evocative campaigns on topical issues such as the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), young farmers and chemicals. An example from this FPN illustrates their public appeal in their pesticide project, where they work with a laboratory to allow people to send in samples of their hair for analysis of pesticide residues. The outcomes of this project were used in a public action in front of the Parliament. On the other hand, the *EU Food Policy Coalition* brings together experts to produce joint letters for policy-makers.

"For us, it's trying to get those combinations of positive impacts on these three areas: on equity and climate and health. [...] So, we're stimulating, we're thinking about themes, these areas, at the time of planning and at the time of delivering action. Basically, at each step they take to be fully aware of ... how your project is going to improve the health status of the people, equity and ambition and climate, or more broadly environmental benefits connected to your intervention. So [...] that's what we're trying to, what we're trying to stimulate cities on" (Interviewee, C40 Food System's Network, global).

National and regional FPNs

The most effective impact for policy change is observed amongst FPNs operating at the national level. This may stem from their positioning at a stable 'mid-level,' where FPNs are neither too large to be ineffective in meeting the needs of numerous stakeholders, nor too small to overlook mid-level policies crucial for driving real change, such as water rights or procurement chains. Furthermore, national-scale FPNs are more likely to capture the cultural values underpinning food systems, including political processes, specific languages and cultural norms.

While at the national level a FPN may wield significant influence in terms of policy, its effectiveness relies on connecting with other levels, particularly city-regional FPNs. This interconnectedness ensures a more holistic and coordinated approach to achieving food system transformation.

It's hard for us to influence [national] policy at that level. So, the tier of government that has been most accessible to us and most amenable to world view and now policy demands has been local government. And that is where we've had the greatest success [...] We're talking to the Minister for Climate change, Energy and Environment [...] So, we've got like [...] an entry into a policy space that [had] previously been [...] largely closed." (Interviewee, Sustain: The Australian Food Network)

City-regional and urban FPNs

City-regional and urban FPNs, the most prevalent scale in this research, often adopt a grassroots and localised approach to addressing regional issues, aligning closely with the first level of change of the framework of transformational capacity (Table 4).

The findings show that city-regional and urban FPNs distribute their efforts between projects and policies. Projects often have a more immediate impact on local food environments compared to policies, which require more time and yield less visible results. Although projects lack the same level of buy-in as policies, they play a crucial role in implementing tangible and immediate changes in the local food environment. These changes serve as the groundwork for establishing trust between stakeholders and the local community.

This division of approaches between project and policy also reflects siloed levels of power: whereas projects are generally acceptable for anyone to undertake, policies often remain within the realm of policy-makers. For example, the interviewee from *Biostädte Netzwerk* (Germany) noted differences in approach between the two cities: in one case, the Senate invited the network to contribute to food strategy discussions, whereas in the second, the focus was only on project work, with limited political involvement. Our findings also show that policy outcomes often arise opportunistically, depending on an FPN's ability to respond to opportunities that may arise. Consequently, many FPNs seek entry points for policy change towards food system transformation goals.

While FPNs may influence food policy through their actions, some FPNs do not see the need to construct their own food policy. For instance, the *Greater Manchester Food Security Action Network* (England), operating at a regional level as a Combined Authority, opted not to draft a policy

statement because the local authorities already have a food strategy. Instead, they are working with the revised *Good Food Greater Manchester* and other stakeholders to implement a Food Programme Board, which addresses issues of food sovereignty, food insecurity and financial inclusion across the wider region. This example underscores that the type of policy action or outcome depends on what is useful and possible within specific city-region food systems.

Finally, an example of multi-level governance is the case of *Mbale Good Food Council and Parliament* (Uganda), which operates through a multi-level decision-making process involving parliamentary and council levels. Resolutions agreed upon at the parliamentary level are implemented and subsequently discussed at the council level for accountability. Legal recognition is formalised through a Memorandum of Understanding with Mbale City leadership, ensuring support for programs. Examples of outcomes include the allocation of land by the city council, a proposal for food ordinances and by-laws, the development and upgrading of market stalls in the central market, the encouragement of backyard gardening in schools and the support for street vendors and informal markets, to improve food safety and access. Once projects are approved by the Parliament, funding becomes available for implementation.

“I do think that our idea of how transformation could succeed is, I wouldn't say, answered conclusively with [our] food strategy, but it goes in that direction. Because that's just how it's thought and structured so that there are four major fields of action. And there are goals in these fields of action. And among the goals there are measures. And underneath there is a vision of where the journey should go. And this vision is, I would say, transformative. It is of course also clear that the urban food system is not detached from the regional or transnational [contexts].” (Interviewee, Ernährungsrat Wien, Austria)

5.3. FPNS' POLICY IMPACT

This sub-section focuses on the last key question of policy approaches for transforming the food system – i.e., policy impact. From the interviews, we have identified four trends of policy impact:

Trend 1: Emphasising process over immediate outcomes

The interviews underscore an emphasis on *process* over immediate policy outcomes. Much effort is devoted to laying the groundwork for policy change, with a significant focus on establishing relationships of trust over time. This finding aligns with the perspective of *Sustainable Food Places* (UK), which emphasises the importance of soft skills, relationship-building and trust-building in influencing policy at the local authority level.

There is a recognition of the need to balance ‘soft’ interventions, such as relationship-building and awareness raising, with ‘hard’ interventions, such as drafting policy documents. This sentiment is echoed by the *C40 Food Systems Network* (global), particularly in their procurement goal, where they highlighted behavioural change as a significant barrier compared to policy change. The interviewee emphasised the importance of gradual steps in introducing changes to allow for public debate and understanding.

“We can't do this work of achieving a better food system that works for everybody unless we look at our internal operations. [...] So, we spent a lot of time on internal operations and organisational development to start with ourselves and like, unlearn the way we were operating. [...] So, it was like not just even our staff. It was like, you know, the 20 plus organisations that are very invested in this work together, let's do it together and we hired a lot of you know, facilitators and we offered a lot of different trainings and like learning groups and things to kind of like, we're going on this journey together.”
(Interviewee, San Diego Food System Alliance, USA)

Trend 2: Nurturing change within and beyond FPNs

Many FPNs also emphasise the importance of both internal (within the FPN) and external (in their local food environment) transformation. The *San Diego Food System Alliance* (USA), for instance, recognised the necessity of intra-organisational change in achieving food system transformation.

“You don't do this overnight. You need to really prepare for how you put this in front of the public and the stakeholders. [...] what we generally advise is a step approach, you know? introducing maybe a Meatless Monday or Friday [...] So, you start with one day you open the public debate around. And then you move to, you know, one day to two days. And then you set a target of say, of maybe two servings of meat per week. [...] And you move gradually towards your goal. And that usually helps the public debate also to evolve and you give time to people to understand. [...] Then, the other thing is like when it comes to, you know, the parents, then you really need a health perspective to guide the public debate.”
(Interviewee, C40 Food Systems Network, global)

Trend 3: Navigating the duality between resistance and reform

Similarly, some FPNs stress the importance of navigating the tension between resisting a harmful capitalist food system and creating just and sustainable alternatives.

“Transformational change on the ground, growing things and operating in non-capitalist ways amongst communities that are just refusing the system as much as we possibly can inside a capitalist system; at the same time, you have to be reforming the structures that are disabling that transformation.”
(Interviewee, Australian Food Sovereignty Alliance)

Trend 4: Balancing the present and the future

Finally, there is also a need to reconcile immediate food security concerns with the long-term goals of food system transformation.

“This very immediate need of hungry people [...] and to coordinate local food networks and emergency food networks and yet wanting to, you know, their work to be transformative. And so, our consultancy advice has been: 'it's OK if your energies right now are in food security, in food aid. But think about the ways in which you could expand beyond that.’” (Interviewee, Sustainable Food Places, UK)

5.4. AN OVERVIEW OF POLICY OUTCOMES

Some of the examined FPNs have achieved various policy outcomes, such as incorporating a food system agenda into local, regional, national and international plans, drafting specific food system strategies and policies or enacting specific food system's ordinances (Table 5).

Table 3: Examples of FPN policy outcomes

POLICY OUTCOMES	EXAMPLES OF SPECIFIC POLICY OUTCOMES
Including a food systems agenda within local, regional, national and international plans	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Lusaka Food Policy Council's</i> (Zambia) Integrated Development Plan • <i>AFSA's</i> (Australia) "55 government submissions " • <i>Biostädte Netzwerk's</i> (Germany) contributions to Berlin's food strategy
Drafting specific food system strategies and policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>C40 Food Systems Network's</i> (global) work with mayors • <i>NICE's</i> (Kenya) support of a food safety strategy in a participating city • <i>Sustain's</i> (Australia) support of local governments in Victoria to draft food system strategies and policies • <i>Denver Sustainable Food Policy Council's</i> (USA) Food Vision • <i>AFSA's</i> (Australia) National People's Food Plan • <i>Sustainable Food Places'</i> (UK) contribution to the national food strategy and support for food partnerships to ensure that they include food system transformation in their charters
Passing specific food system ordinances	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Comité Municipal de Seguridad Alimentaria's</i> (Bolivia) creation of food policy positions in/with local government • <i>CChicago Food Policy Action Council's</i> (USA) advocacy for allowing mobile markets. and vendors (i.e. mobile food pantries) • <i>Mbale Good Food Council and Parliament's</i> (Uganda) Good Food Purchasing Programmes

Even after achieving food policy outcomes, the journey continues for FPNs. Some policies remain aspirational, serving as frameworks for future action, rather than as immediately transformative measures. For example, a representative from the *Red de Municipios por la Agroecología* (Spain) critiqued the soft nature of many municipal food policies, which are "neither transforming the food system, nor are they helping people to have a better right to healthy and sustainable food, nor are they improving people's diets. They are very half-hearted actions with very little budget" (interviewee).

Even when policies are enacted, challenges persist. *Food Secure Canada*, for instance, found that although they successfully established a Food Policy for Canada and a Food Policy Advisory Council, corporate interests continued to wield significant influence outside of these structures.

Similarly, in Chicago (*Food Policy Action Council*, USA), policy implementation was hindered by a lack of capacity and commitment from government bodies.

“Either they were stopped, or the political efforts were stopped completely, proposals were withdrawn and the CAP reform [...] did not live up to our expectation” (Interviewee, GFGF)

In certain instances, FPNs experienced policy failures in their advocacy efforts. For instance, during their campaigns for pesticide regulation, an EU sustainable food system framework and CAP reform, a GFGF representative mentioned that they faced serious opposition and initial success were reversed.

These setbacks underscore the ongoing nature of the fight for food system transformation. FPNs recognise the need for continued effort, potentially through alternative strategies or by engaging new stakeholders. These experiences also highlight the cyclical process of policy formation, emphasising the importance of monitoring, reinforcing and reflecting on outcomes to advance towards their goals.

6. BARRIERS AND LESSONS LEARNT

6.1. BARRIERS

Addressing food insecurity and improving food systems requires a multifaceted approach, yet several significant barriers often hinder progress. According to FPNs, the most common barriers faced by initiatives aimed at enhancing food policy are the lack of resources, maintaining stakeholder engagement, and frequent changes in elected officials. For FPNs, the lack of resources predominantly centres on limited human resources and financial constraints. Moreover, maintaining the active engagement of a diverse range of stakeholders in the work of FPNs remains a persistent challenge. Finally, advocating for long-term change within institutional settings that lack stability in terms of support from government officials and policy priorities due to short-term policy cycles has emerged as a common barrier for FPNs. These challenges collectively impede the implementation and sustainability of effective food policies, necessitating strategic solutions to overcome them. This discussion will delve into each of these barriers, exploring their impact on food policy efforts and potential strategies to mitigate their effects.

Lack of resources

The most significant barrier faced by FPNs is the lack of funding to support their efforts, both within and outside government institutions. While it may be assumed that FPNs operating within government would enjoy greater financial stability, this is not always the case. About a third of FPNs in the UK's *Sustainable Food Places Network* are situated within local authorities. Although these FPNs benefit from a demonstrated commitment to food systems, they still grapple with securing funding, especially given the financial constraints and fiscal challenges that many local authorities in the UK currently face, including bankruptcy or the necessity for match funding.

FPNs in locales such as the *Mesa de Coordinación del Pacto de Milán de Córdoba* (Spain) emphasised the imperative for action to be accompanied by budget allocations, lamenting the difficulty in effecting change without the necessary financial backing. This pursuit of financial security poses a conundrum for government-hosted FPNs, potentially hampering their ability to engage in politically driven campaigns due to constraints and concerns about maintaining relationships with local authorities. In several instances, municipal bodies are unable or unwilling to support the "slightly radical edge" of food partnership work (*Sustainable Food Places* (UK) interviewee), which is further exacerbated by historical power imbalances eroding trust between civil society organisations and local authorities. FPNs hosted in community organisations often face more insecure funding but enjoy greater freedom to campaign and advocate politically. However, they may encounter difficulties in engaging with local authorities and securing senior political buy-in.

The majority of FPNs rely on volunteers and underpaid part-time employees to maintain their day-to-day operations, leading to issues such as burnout and lack of continuity. The absence of sustained or additional funding also prevents FPNs from undertaking more ambitious actions, such as large-scale events and campaigns. For instance, *Uganda Food Change Lab's* representative recognised the necessity for sustained resources to implement innovations and address issues such as policy enforcement and monitoring. Similarly, the interviewee from *Sustainable Food Places* (UK) noted that FPNs often rely on overloaded part-time employees who struggle to fulfil the network's full potential.

To address funding shortfalls, FPNs may explore hybrid structures (i.e., combining elements of a foundation, social enterprise or charity) or pursue grants. However, this approach may lead to fragmented efforts and limit their focus to short-term, issue-specific projects.

Maintaining stakeholder engagement

The second most common barrier faced by FPNs is their ability to engage stakeholders in food system transformation, essentially encapsulating the challenge of mobilising people to care and take action. Significant efforts are required to raise awareness, understand stakeholders' perspectives and foster collaboration around shared interests, values and goals. This engagement spans collaborations with funders, farmers and the general public.

FPNs encounter difficulties in collaboration when stakeholders defend their own interests, as noted by one interviewee from the *Ghent Food Policy Council* (Belgium). Additionally, competing priorities can hinder engagement, as observed by a member of *Our Food Network Dunedin* (New Zealand). As noted by this interviewee, inclusive engagement is also crucial to overcoming issues of privilege. Various strategies are employed to appeal to different groups and communities, including storytelling and leadership development, as exemplified by the *GFGF* (Europe) and *Healthy Savannah* (USA), respectively.

Government stakeholders are often cited as the most challenging to engage. *Biostädte Netzwerk* (Germany) and *Cork Food Policy Council* (Ireland) note prevailing attitudes that view food as solely an economic issue rather than a political one. Similarly, *Sustain's Australian Food Network* highlighted the lack of national policy agendas for food, which makes it difficult to secure resources for transformative initiatives. To overcome this challenge, the *Mbale Good Food Parliament* (Uganda) employs one-on-one facilitation to motivate and involve members, while also gaining recognition and support from top city leadership for their endeavours.

Changing elected officials

After gaining support from policymakers and municipalities, FPNs often face the challenge of navigating changes in elected officials. A representative from the *San Diego Food System Alliance* (USA) described how they have experienced a constant turnover of elected officials over the past decade, leading to the need to continually re-establish relationships with different departments and individuals. Similar situations were reported by FPNs in Australia (*Fair Food Illawarra*), Latin

America (*Plataforma Multi-actor Lima*, Peru), Africa (*FLAC*, Kenya) and Europe (*Consell Alimentari Municipal de València* and *Consejo Alimentario Municipal de Zaragoza*, Spain).

This turnover is particularly challenging because food policy issues require long-term solutions, which are not always aligned with the short-term nature of politics. As noted by the *Nutrire Trento's* (Italy) representative, the timing of political cycles often conflicts with the long-term nature of addressing food policy issues. In short, broader bureaucratic processes can impede progress in terms of the policy and advocacy work of FPNs.

Other barriers

Less frequently mentioned but equally crucial barriers for the FPNs include:

1. **Managing representation and diversity:** FPNs must navigate how to best represent the diverse perspectives and interests of various groups within their communities. Moreover, FPNs face cultural barriers that can inhibit certain stakeholders' ability to participate fully.
2. **Fragmentation in food policy:** The food justice and sustainability agendas suffer from overall fragmentation, hindering cohesive action. In some FPNs, fragmentation can be seen in the prioritisation of certain food issues over others. For instance, the *Lusaka Food Policy Council* (Zambia) noted there is often a dominant focus on agricultural issues in their policy discussions. Another barrier that exacerbates the challenges of a fragmented food policy environment is the lack of overall coordination across stakeholders and government departments involved in food policy.
3. **Measuring and communicating impact:** FPNs struggle with measuring and conveying their impact to decision-makers and funders. As a result, FPNs may face criticism for focusing on dialogue and deliberation processes without resulting in tangible outcomes.

These barriers highlight **power dynamics** that affect FPNs' ability to include certain groups and affect food system transformation. Power imbalances in the food systems, which tend to be dominated by the industry and supermarkets, are identified as a significant challenge due to their dominant market position and influence. The *Good Food Fund China*, for instance, advocates for "food freedom" to counteract corporate dominance in the food industry. Similarly, an interviewee from *Sustainable Food Places* (UK) acknowledged the acute awareness of the immense power disparities when engaging with supermarkets, stating: "you can't change national, international supermarket policy generally speaking [...] it's just a massive appropriation of these partnerships [...] They're not equal relationships."

To avoid frustration with power imbalances, FPNs often focus on pushing through achievable pathways to change with the available resources and stakeholders' interests. For example, the *Denver Sustainable Food Policy Council* (USA) aims to engage with policy-makers early to prevent wasted effort on rejected policies.

6.2. LESSONS LEARNT

Interviewees shared their insights on the key lessons they have learned and their recommendations for other FPNs. From their responses, we have distilled seven key lessons, which we discuss in descending order of popularity in this section. To provide a quick overview, we have also summarised these lessons and their corresponding strategies in Table 6.

Embracing the long journey: Accepting the timeframe of food system transformation

Recognising the inherent complexities of effecting systemic change, many FPNs highlighted the relevance of accepting that transformation takes time. This sentiment is expressed by a member of the *San Diego Food System Alliance* (USA), underscoring the significance of investing in relationship-building and fostering trust among stakeholders. They emphasise that building trust in an authentic, transparent way can lay the foundation for collaborative efforts that sustain momentum over what may be a decades-long journey, as emphasised by *Food Secure Canada*.

Time is also necessary to transition from an individualistic mindset to a collective perspective, which is seen as pivotal for fostering mutual understanding and co-creation among partners. Additionally, time is considered crucial for the internal development of the FPN, as explained by a representative of the *Cork Food Policy Council* (Ireland). They described a progression over the years, starting with establishing and presenting the FPN, then engaging with stakeholders, followed by being relevant and responsive to what is happening on the ground. Eventually, the FPN reaches a point where initiatives “come to them” rather than constantly being pursued. The member in *Mesa de Coordinación del Pacto de Milán de Córdoba* (Spain) compared this journey to a “pick and shovel” endeavour, acknowledging the inevitable setbacks and challenges inherent in effecting change.

To navigate the complexities associated with such long-term goals, FPNs propose several strategic approaches:

- **Planning short and medium-term goals** to achieve incremental successes and maintain momentum, while simultaneously aspiring towards broader objectives.
- **Prioritising goals** to ensure optimal allocation of resources and attention to avoid “getting bogged down or focusing on the things that you can't do or you don't have the sort of power or autonomy to do” (*Denver Sustainable Food Policy Council*, USA).

Remaining adaptable and seizing opportunities as they arise, particularly in engaging policy-makers and responding to shifting political landscapes.

- **Maintaining a consistent and appropriate level of engagement and activity** within the FPN – i.e., a frequency “that is neither too high nor too low” (interviewee *Red de Municipios por la Agroecología*, Spain) – to ensure continuity and sustainability efforts.
- **Securing long-term funding and resources** to support collaborative efforts over time, as emphasised by *Uganda Food Change Lab*.

Local context matters: Tailoring strategies to unique environments

Each FPN operates within a unique context that is shaped by factors such as cultural awareness, political landscape or resource availability. It is therefore essential for FPNs to tailor their approaches and goals to their specific circumstances. For example, *Sustainable Food Places* (UK) acknowledges the diversity of food systems across the different regions within the UK, emphasising the importance of not feeling overwhelmed by attempting to fix the whole thing. Instead, the interviewee highlighted the importance of focusing on localised efforts that harness the unique energies and priorities of each community.

To address their contextual specificity, FPNs employ various strategies:

- **Building social capital:** Recognising that food is deeply intertwined with culture, community and identity, FPNs prioritise relationships and trust within their communities. *Good Food Fund China*, for instance, emphasises the importance of understanding local food cultures and engaging with communities at a personal level. Initiatives such as training targeted public servants about sustainable food systems serve to raise awareness and foster support from key stakeholders (*Rete PunTO al Cibo* and *Nutrire Trento*, Italy). Others acknowledged the importance of re-framing food system issues “without describing it as a flawed system” (*Ons Eten Den Haag* and *Voedsel Anders*, The Netherlands).
- **Allowing FPNs to arise organically:** Rather than imposing top-down approaches, FPNs recognise the importance of grassroots movements and original groundswells support. The representative from *Sustainable Food Places* (UK) emphasises the need for FPNs to grow naturally from within the community, ensuring genuine engagement and long-term sustainability.
- **Recognising champions and celebrating successes:** Key individuals play a crucial role in driving change. Whether they are founders, city officials or dedicated volunteers, champions are instrumental in pushing FPNs forward. Recognising and celebrating their contributions not only acknowledge their efforts but also foster a sense of community and social capital, as highlighted by various FPNs’ representatives – i.e., *Cork Food Policy Council* (Ireland), *Nourish Scotland*, *Comitato Promotore per una Food Policy di Roma* (Italy), *Harleem Food Future* (The Netherlands), *NICE* (International).
- **Adapting key learnings from others:** Rather than reinventing the wheel, FPNs often leverage existing resources and best practices from other networks and initiatives. Documentation and toolkits, such as those provided by *Sustainable Food Places* (UK), serve as valuable guides for setting up and implementing initiatives in new contexts. Participating in network events such as those organised for German-speaking FPNs offers valuable opportunities for knowledge-exchange and peer learning. By adapting and building upon the experiences of others, FPNs can streamline their efforts and maximise impact.

Inclusivity in action: Balancing participation and key stakeholder involvement

Participation by diverse stakeholders is integral to fostering shared knowledge, understanding and collaborative problem-solving (as explained by an interviewee from FLAC). Such inclusive approaches enrich individual perspectives and facilitate the exchange of insights, ultimately nurturing a culture of shared information. Interviewees from *Ceinture Aliment-Terre Liègeoise* (Belgium), *Ons Eten den Haag* and *Voedsel Anders* (The Netherlands) advocated for strategies that embrace inclusivity and avoid top-down approaches. This involves co-creating food strategies with a wide range of stakeholders, thereby harnessing collective expertise and perspectives. Other FPNs' representatives (i.e., *Greater Manchester Food Security Action Network*, England) advised maintaining a balance between inclusive participation and strategic selection of stakeholders to enable progress.

To balance inclusive participation and the involvement of key stakeholders, the following strategies are identified:

- **Aligning with FPNs' goals:** Stakeholders should align with the specific objectives of the FPN, whether they are politically influential entities (such as mayors in *C40 Food Systems Network*) or marginalised groups such as women and children – as exemplified by the *Arusha Food Safety Committee* (Tanzania). Building “*long-term relationships with funders*” (*Open Food Network* interviewee, Australia and New Zealand) who financially support the activities and operations of FPNs (i.e., government entities, non-profit organisations or foundations) or monitoring “*big food players who develop other agendas on these themes*” (*Rete PunTO al Cibo* interviewee, Italy) were also recommended.
- **Providing different levels of engagement:** Stakeholders may vary in capacity and expertise, and this raises the need for flexible approaches to engagement. This could involve having larger organisations initiate actions that smaller entities can join or contribute to, as highlighted by the *EU Food Policy Coalition* interviewee.
- **Embracing a diversity of perspectives:** Recognising that stakeholders may have differing values and approaches, collaboration should be inclusive and respectful. The *Open Food Network* (Australia and New Zealand) interviewee, for instance, recommends specialising and collaborating based on strengths, while the *EU Food Policy Coalition* representative emphasises the importance of engaging stakeholders from all sides of the debate to negotiate meaningful progress. Fostering dialogue and understanding among diverse stakeholders is also key to progressing food system transformation. The *GFGF* (Europe) interviewee underscores the importance of avoiding a “*bubble aspect*” where assumptions about shared values may not hold true. Instead, FPNs should prioritise inclusive dialogue where differing opinions are respected and joint solutions are forged.

Government engagement strategies: Connecting with and across government departments and levels

Whether based within or outside of government, several FPNs recognised the importance of engaging with and across government departments to influence policy and resource allocation toward food system change. This collaboration is seen as essential for effective implementation by *Consell Alimentari Municipal de València* (Spain) and *Biostädte Netzwerk* (Germany).

FPNs highlighted the significance of local government buy-in, with *FLAC* (Kenya) interviewee noting its pivotal role. However, engagement with higher levels of governance, such as national or continental, can be challenging. Some FPN representatives cautioned against becoming overly fixated on government involvement unless there are potential funding opportunities or specific regulatory barriers that necessitate focused action, as advised by the *Open Food Network* (Australia and New Zealand) interviewee.

Strategies to facilitate connections within and across government departments include:

- **Navigating bureaucracy efficiently:** Many interviewees stressed the importance of identifying the relevant departments and framing requests in clear, actionable terms. The *AFSA* (Kenya) interviewee underscored the need to approach the right department with specific asks, maintaining persistence while balancing patience.
- **Engaging with politics:** The *Biostädte Netzwerk* (Germany) representative, amongst others, suggested adopting a more political approach or becoming more 'institutionalised' to effectively communicate with councils. This may involve providing documents or proposals that align with governmental priorities and are more likely to gain traction.
- **Creating transversal strategies:** Some FPNs advocated for strategies that demonstrate how food-related issues intersect with various levels of governance. This could involve raising internal awareness within municipalities through training programmes or establishing dedicated food policy offices, as exemplified by *Nutrire Trento* (Italy).
- **Framing issues inclusively:** The *ShelfFood* (England) interviewee recommended adopting broad definitions of food-related issues *"that create a movement and recognise the synergies and overlaps between them all."* Along the same lines, the *C40 Food Systems Network* (global) representative underscored the importance of integrating equity and climate considerations into food policy discussions to address the interconnected challenges facing communities.

Creative budget solutions: Maximising impact with limited resources

To address the pervasive challenge of budgetary constraints, FPNs have devised several strategies:

- **Prioritising essential activities:** Some FPNs emphasised the importance of budgeting for essential activities while being mindful of costs and objectives. The *Red de Municipios por la Agroecología* (Spain) interviewee advised careful consideration of funding allocation, urging against over-ambitious goals and excessive participation. Similarly, the representative from *Sustainable Food Places* (UK) highlighted the need to have at least one paid coordinator to ensure effective coordination and implementation.
- **Exploring alternative economic models:** Many FPNs have adopted plural economic forms to sustain their activities. This diversification of funding sources helps reduce reliance on traditional funding streams and enhances financial resilience.
- **Recognising opportunities without a budget:** Some interviewees highlighted the importance of what can be accomplished without significant funding. The *Cork Food Policy Council* (Ireland)

interviewee, for example, challenged the notion that funding is always essential, suggesting that reliance on funding can hinder progress due to bureaucratic constraints. Instead, the interviewee recommended starting with a core group of committed individuals and developing a shared vision through inclusive dialogue. By leveraging creativity and commitment, FPNs can overcome resource limitations and drive meaningful change.

Internal harmony, external impact: Cultivating transparency and empowerment

FPNs are increasingly focused on aligning their internal operations with their values and approaches to foster trust and commitment. Strategies for enhancing internal dynamics include:

- **Embracing transparency:** Several FPNs recognised the importance of transparency in building trust with the community. FPN representatives (such as the one from the *San Diego Food System Alliance*, USA) emphasised the significance of being open about internal operations and organisational structures. By being transparent, FPNs can foster greater community engagement and collaboration.
- **Empowering stakeholders through facilitation:** Several FPNs prioritised empowering stakeholders by facilitating dialogue, networking opportunities and knowledge-sharing. The interviewee from the *Good Food Fund China*, for instance, emphasised the role of facilitation in driving collaboration, learning and the development of joint food projects and funding opportunities.
- **Formalising internal practices:** Most FPNs solidified their values and approaches within internal documents such as vision statements and engagement policies. Some FPNs (i.e., the *Islington Food Partnership*, England) highlighted the importance of establishing clear guidelines for engagement and decision-making processes to ensure inclusivity and mitigate potential conflict. By formalising internal practices, FPNs can create a supportive and inclusive environment for stakeholders to actively participate and contribute.

From words to deeds: Implementing concrete actions for change

Finally, many interviewees emphasised the importance of going beyond mere talk and policy writing to actively participate in hands-on change within local communities. Key strategies recommended include:

- **Participating in direct action campaigns:** Getting involved in direct action campaigns allows FPNs and their members to step away from strategic planning and engage directly in tangible activities. For example, the *Islington Food Partnership* (England) interviewee highlighted the benefits of being actively involved in direct actions to foster a mindset of taking concrete steps toward change.
- **Organising citizen's assemblies and workshops:** Some interviewees, such as the representative from *Ernährungszukunft Schweiz* (Switzerland), advocated for organising citizens' assemblies that involve physical and online workshops, learning journeys and project visits. These assemblies provide opportunities for participants to gain first-hand experience and understand the food system, fostering informed engagement and collaboration.

Creating alternative food centres: FPNs such as the *Australian Food Network* or *Edible Canterbury* (New Zealand) have taken action by establishing alternative food centres, such as urban farms. The *Australian Food Network* interviewee described their approach as going beyond research and words to actively setting up and managing urban farms, converting barren sites into thriving market gardens and transforming abandoned spaces into productive areas. This hands-on experience not only informs their advocacy efforts but also lends credibility and depth to their engagement with local governments and food policy discussions.

Table 4: A summary of lessons learnt and strategies to overcome barriers by FPNs.

LESSON LEARNT	SPECIFIC STRATEGIES
<i>Embracing the long journey</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning short and medium-term goals • Prioritising goals • Remaining adaptable and seizing opportunities • Maintaining a consistent and appropriate level of engagement and activity • Securing long-term funding and resources
<i>Local context matters</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building social capital • Allowing FPNs to arise organically • Recognising champions and celebrating successes • Adapting key learnings from others
<i>Inclusivity in action</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aligning with FPN goals • Providing different levels of engagement • Embracing a diversity of perspectives
<i>Government engagement strategies</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Navigating bureaucracy efficiently • Engaging with politics • Creating transversal strategies • Framing issues inclusively
<i>Creative budget solutions</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritising essential activities • Exploring alternative economic models • Recognising opportunities without a budget
<i>Internal harmony, external impact</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Embracing transparency • Empowering stakeholders through facilitation • Formalising internal practices

From words to deeds

- Participating in direct action campaigns
- Organising citizen's assemblies and workshops
- Creating alternative food centres

7. CONCLUSIONS

Our findings highlight the internal diversity of the global food movement, with a wide array of compositional types of FPNs that share a broad commitment to inclusion and transformation but widely differ in terms of specific objectives and strategies. Depending on the scale at which FPNs operate, the inclusion of marginalised communities and vulnerable groups is pursued primarily through school food programmes, the development of urban and peri-urban (agriculture) initiatives, the organisation of food-related events and food education initiatives. No matter what strategy is deployed, FPNs identify financial and logistical barriers that make it very difficult for them to connect with communities outside traditional spheres.

To circumvent such barriers, FPNs strive to establish context-specific and effective strategies (Table 6). Key examples include identifying pragmatic objectives for food system transformation through the identification of short- and medium-term goals and the adoption of step-by-step approaches; prioritising action agendas tailored to local opportunities and available resources; embracing diverse perspectives while providing different levels of engagement to promote and secure participation from multiple stakeholders; developing government engagement strategies that prioritise how to navigate bureaucracy across government departments and levels; devising creative and pragmatic budget solutions for maximising the impact of limited resources and identifying opportunities for action even in periods of economic instability; formalising internal guidelines to ensure transparency and meaningful participation in decision-making processes; and prioritising hands-on change and practical collaborations with and for the local communities.

Taken together, these strategies highlight everyday governance mechanisms that enable future visions for sustainable food systems to be performed in the present. A key lesson is that enacting desired food systems through everyday practices and relationships can foster a heightened critical consciousness of the inherently political nature of food system transformations and that, beyond acquiring more material and financial resources, it is essential to strengthen capacities to address power relations. Enhanced inclusion of marginalised and vulnerable citizens is one of the three strategies adopted by FPNs to strengthen their transformative capacity. The other two intra-organisational changes that have been enacted over time to achieve such a goal include an effort to develop a more comprehensive perspective (i.e., to adopt a food system lens) as well as to become more action oriented. In some cases, these strategies have enabled FPNs to achieve policy outcomes – i.e., the development of a food system’s agenda at the local, regional, national or international level, the drafting of specific food system strategies and policies and the passing of specific ordinances.

In all, however, these tend to be isolated and often fragile gains. Indeed, our analysis shows that barriers persist, primarily around the lack of resources, the difficulties of sustaining

stakeholders' engagement and the challenge of navigating changes in elected officials. The ongoing efforts within FPNs to develop context-sensitive strategies, balance the participation of key stakeholders, adopt creative budget solutions (i.e., diversification of funding sources and prioritising essential activities) and embrace transparency need to be cemented around a wider, transformative agenda that begins to question the underlying power imbalances that shape the food system.

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9. APPENDIX

9.1. THE GUIDELINES FOR THE LITERATURE REVIEW

Aim

This comprehensive literature review seeks to innovatively focus on: (1) the composition of different types of FPNs, with particular attention to the mechanisms that have been deployed to enhance participation of representatives from vulnerable and deprived groups; and (2) their capacity to initiate and support change in the urban food environment as a leverage point to transform the urban food system.

Process of the review

- This review is being conducted by project partners in different languages, where these guidelines serve to provide some comparability across the research results for analysis.
- This search is for FPNs in cities throughout the world. To explore their full diversity, you may wish to draw on knowledge from FPNs in your own city to see if they exist elsewhere. You are welcome to add more search terms than suggested for this.
- Two documents are provided: (1) These guidelines, and (2) An excel datasheet template.
- The process is divided into 2 steps: conducting the review and synthesising the data. First, please use these guidelines to find FPNs through the literature search, and second, please fill out as many details as possible for the FPNs in the excel spreadsheet.
- Please record all data and any notes in the excel spreadsheet as you go and return the spreadsheet to Surrey team.
- The goal of the task is to find diverse FPNs that currently exist in each region where all relevant approaches for this outcome can be used. Please do add a comment in the excel spreadsheet on why and how the FPNs were sourced.

Conducting the review

- 1) To first choose an academic source/s to search for data (such as Google Scholar or Web of Science). This data may be supplemented by additional data search using policy and grey literature, such as project reports, case studies, handbooks and/or information briefs that relate to FPNs.

- 2) To translate the key search terms within the year range of the last 10 years in the table below into your native language – see column below for translated terms. Please note that 10 years is a general guide – other articles outside this timeframe may be used if they provide better information and refer to FPNs that are still in existence. Please also take notes in the excel spreadsheet if there are significant translation issues. For example, do terms have the same or different connotations in different languages? Are there different cultural preferences for urban food policy examples in different cities? Are new terms needed to address urban food policy in different cities? If so, what are these and explain how they differ.
- 3) To first search for a diverse range of FPNs, you can use the suggested search terms in category 1 of table 1 to locate the articles. Other terms may also be used that are more specific to the characteristics of FPNs in your region. As FPNs may be multi-scalar, we suggest elements and/or features of them should relate to urban and/or city-regions. Search for category 1 and conduct an initial scan to meet a set of criteria (i.e., document source, document type, minimum one paragraph description of FPNs).
- 4) Next focus the search on FPN’s engagement with vulnerable and deprived groups (i.e., the FoodCLIC aspect of inclusion of citizens (including in particular marginalised and vulnerable groups) in the design, implementation and monitoring of policies). To meet this objective, use key terms listed in category 2 in table 7.
- 5) Finally, refine the search to explore the FPN’s transformational capacity (see category 3; combine search terms from categories 1 and 3).
- 6) Record data about this literature in the excel spreadsheet in English following the headings.
- 7) The first sheet (‘selection’) may also include articles that are relevant but do not fall exactly within the categories (for example, they may provide a great overview of FPNs). Colour coding can be used to denote relevancy: green = relevant; orange = some but not high relevancy. Please also add a comment of their relevancy in excel sheet.
- 8) It is also important to add comments. For example, of key features or relevance of the article or of any highlights or concerns about this process. If you see gaps in the FPNs you are researching, you may also propose questions for interviews.

Table 7: Search categories and suggested key search terms

Category and definition	Suggested key search terms in English. <i>Please adapt these terms to your region’s language and characteristics.</i>
‘Food policy networks’ (FPNs) are defined in the DOA as being “endorsed by relevant institutions from the quadruple helix – can constitute a broad and inclusive SPPI that generates transformative knowledge, supports the formulation and implementation of	Food policy network; food policy assemblages; urban food policy; urban food strategies; community food system; translocal food governance; food policy council; food security policy; urban food policy; local food network; food innovation network; food safety policies; alternative food network; community food network;

<p>integrated urban food policies and empowers food system actors around a shared vision of the urban food system”.</p> <p>For this task, we are interested in city-region and/or urban FPNs.</p> <p><i>TO NOTE that this task aims to look at diverse FPNs that may not fit this exact definition. Please use the suggested terms in column 2 to find diverse examples in your region and please make notes in the comments section about how they relate to this general definition.</i></p>	<p>urban farming policy/network; urban agriculture policy/network; food waste policy/network; community supported agriculture policy/council/network; food + local environment policy/network/council; public procurement policy/network/council; fair trade policy/network/council; food sharing network/council; sustainable food policy/ network/council; environmental food policy/council/network; ecological food policy/council/network; urban food regime.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">AND</p> <p>City; city region; urban (possibly, also: municipal; council; local government).</p>
<p>Vulnerable and deprived groups: Inclusion of all food system actors and citizens, while ensuring also a fairer distribution of its outcomes.</p>	<p>Vulnerable/deprived groups; migrants; the elderly; school children; food insecure. + participation, inclusion/inclusive, exclusion, equity/equitable, integrated, representation</p>
<p>Transformational capacity of FPNs</p>	<p>Food system change; transition; transformation; social change; circular cities; socio-ecological change/transition; system change.</p>

- 9) Enter data from the literature review into the spreadsheet on FPNs in English following the headings (you can include key terms in your native language here too). It is likely that you will need to use more than 1 data source to complete each FPN profile.
- 10) It is also important to note if and how the FPNs integrate with other aspects along the FoodCLIC framework – i.e., co-benefits between economic, social and environmental objectives; linkages between urban, peri-urban and rural areas and between the land and the sea; inclusion (introduced above) and connectivity between the food system and other sectors and policies, such as waste, water and the built environment. If sufficient data are available, fill in details in the spreadsheet about other aspects of the CLIC framework (see table 8). You may use the suggested guiding questions below to help you engage with the CLIC dimensions.

Table 8: CLIC framework dimensions and guiding questions

CLIC framework	
C – Co-benefits	What kind of objectives (i.e., economic, social and environmental) do the FPNs pursue? Are they interrelated? And if so, how?
L – Linkages	Are FPNs creating or strengthening linkages between urban, peri-urban and rural areas? And if so, how? If applicable, are FPNs creating or strengthening linkages between land and sea? And if so, how?
I – Inclusion	Who is included in the FPNs?

	Do FPNs have any strategy to include marginalised groups? And if so, how are they planning to do it – or doing – it?
C – Connectivities	<p>Do FPNs bring together different groups of stakeholders within the city-region?</p> <p>Do FPNs collaborate with different departments of the City administration? What about with departments at other levels (i.e., regional, national or international)?</p> <p>Do FPNs participate in (food) policy in the city-region? What about in other levels (i.e., regional, national or international)?</p>

- 11) During the search, a key person or group who would be highly relevant for an interview may become apparent. If so, please add their details in the provided column.
- 12) While searching literature for your region, you may find literature for others. Please place any articles in the MS Teams folder ‘articles for other regions’ and identify the folder with the name of the country.

9.2. THE INTERVIEW SCHEDULE

To the interviewer: Please re-interpret the interview schedule into your own language. Please describe any change of terms that may change meaning in translation.

- Language notes:
- The questions below form a guide for discussion. They are ‘open’ questions used to prompt interviewees to describe their FPNs and related activities. Please do not assume that interviewees share the same understanding of key concepts and definitions – its best to encourage the interviewee to describe their interpretation of these in their own words.
- Please audio record all interviews.
- We recommend that interviews are approx. 45 (and should not last more than an hour).
- Please make sure the interviewee has signed the consent form before the interview.
- Please take notes as you go. Please scan and send any notes to us after the interview.
- After the interview, please send the completed first page of this form, the transcript in English and any notes to: f.edwards@surrey.ac.uk and also upload to the MS Teams.

To be filled out by the interviewer:

Name of interviewee, their FPN and their email address

Name of interviewer and organisation:

Date and place of interview:

Introduction: This is meant to be an informal discussion and we have some guiding questions to help this. You don't need to respond in detail to all of them, and feel free to skip any of them. You are not required to answer any questions if you do not feel comfortable.

A) The purpose and scope of the FPN:

1. You describe yourself as a [i.e., network, council, coalition, etc.]? Why did you decide to call yourself this type of organisation? Has this name changed over time and if so, why?
2. Could you please describe in a few words what the FPN's purpose is and how you plan to achieve this?
3. What kind of legal entity is the FPN and since when (if not a legal entity, why not)? How is leadership organized in the FPN? (Who or which body within the FPN holds decision-making power)
4. What would you say are the key events in the history of the FPN?
5. What is the membership of your FPN? How can people/organisations become members?
6. Does your FPN work with government? Could you please describe this relationship.

Prompts: If so, what level of government? What degree of control/flexibility is there in your relationship? When and where does government play a role? Which group (your FPN or the government or another again) instigated the network? On reflection, would you work more or less with government if you could start over? Please describe how.

7. What links does the FPN have to your city, other cities or with other groups? How do you keep these relationships engaged?

Prompts: Geographically, where does your FPN work?

8. In what ways have other actors, institutions or infrastructures, such as existing FPNs, policies and planning frameworks, inspired, supported or hampered your FPN?

B) Inclusion:

FoodCLIC is very interested in 'inclusion', such as including residents in the design, participation and evaluation of policies, and how your FPN provides activities across the city-region.

9. Do you think that your FPN is currently inclusive? Please describe how.

Prompts: What type of inclusion does it represent? I.e., Are particular groups in your city being included in the FPN? I.e., People who are disadvantaged economically, the elderly, children or others? Where are they located in the city? At what stage in the decision-making process of the FPN do these and/or other groups have a say? How is their feedback integrated into the design, implementation and evaluation of the FPN? Are there other areas of the city-region that you feel could benefit more from your work?

10. How do you think inclusiveness could be improved in the FPN?

Prompts: What types of (social and spatial) inclusiveness could be amplified? Why these in particular? Are there any barriers for expanding your FPN in this way? How would you like to include these groups? I.e. What steps or processes would your FPN establish to do this?

C) Transformation:

The FoodCLIC project is interested in how we can transform the food system to become more inclusive and environmentally sustainable. We are particularly interested in how your FPN is involved in changing your 'food environment', i.e., this is how your local food options looks. I.e. They could be wild, institutional, community-based, corporate, etc.

11. Could you please describe if and what actions your FPN may be involved in to change your local food environment?

Prompts: Examples of activities of such change could involve community gardens, setting up seed swaps, community fridges, planting fruit trees or food sharing events. Is your FPN doing any of these or similar other types of activities?

12. How is your FPN involved in influencing or impact change at the policy level? What transformational actions (either in the food environmental or at a policy level) would you would like to make?

Prompts: What could these look like? What benefits would they provide? Do you think they'd be barriers for implementing them?

13. Overall, what key lessons have you learnt from your FPN that you would advise others? What has been your greatest failure and how have you learnt from this?

14. Overall, what key barriers has your FPN experienced and how do you suggest overcoming them? What do you perceive the future to be like for your FPN?

D) A big thankyou and information about follow-up.

That's pretty much the bulk of the interview.

15. Are you happy for us to contact you if we have any questions in the future?

Of course, if you have any follow up questions or would like to add any further clarification to your answers, please do not hesitate to contact us. Thank you so much for your time today!

PARTNERS

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#foodclik

Funded
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